

Coworkers' Perceptions of Involves Communicating

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ABSTRACT

Suggestion towards improvement of organizational communication was also assessed by the employees themselves. Positive attitude come out as the most important suggestion for better organisational output by the employees. E-mail was found to be the overall most preferred mode of communication and fax being the least preferred one. However, Government people relied most on written communications and telephone communication was preferred in non-government organisations. Both government and non-government employees ranked video conferencing as the weakest mode of communication. Language and medium used are found to be the most common barriers, which hamper the communication process in all the three organisations i.e Government, Non-Government and Corporate. Technological advancements have made the communication faster and better in almost all the organisations. However, the traditional office culture of Government organisation is also changing so as to keep pace with other two organisations. Communication flow equipped with sound technical knowledge on computer can lead to better performance of employees in organisations. The present study focuses on the different modes, and barriers of communication in organizations and how employee's suggestions, recommendations and feedback lead to increased productivity of the employees and better organisational performance.

Key words: Assess, Barrier, Communication, Mode, Organisation.

INTRODUCTION

The process of sharing knowledge and clear definition from one person to another is known as communication. Effective communication is a two-way process that needs both sender and receiver effort and talent. The sender, encoding the message, transferring the message through a medium, receiving the message, decoding the message, and feedback are all parts of the communication process. A lot of impediments exist in the workplace that prevent efficient communication. To improve communication effectiveness, the elements related with this should be avoided. Employees working in a specific environment can estimate the severity of such elements and prioritise them.

With the foregoing in mind, the current study aims to rank modes of communication and impediments to communication in the workplace by employees themselves, with the goal of prioritising proposals for improving organisational communication.

Research methodology

The current research was carried out in Delhi. The current study includes data from 154 individuals from three distinct types of firms who were chosen at random.

RESULT DISCUSSION

When all of the organisations were considered, the results revealed that e-mail was the most favoured means of communication and fax was the least preferred. Between these two, other modes of communication were inserted. In corporate sectors, almost comparable preferences were seen; however, written circulars were found to be the most favoured means of communication in government organisations, whereas telephone communication was favoured in non-government organisations. Video conferencing was considered as the weakest means of communication by both government and non-government personnel, followed by fax and individual feedback. As a result of the company's goal-setting agenda, practical achievable plans, proper human resources management, monitoring progress, employee performance appraisal, good communication atmosphere, and control over realisation, these kinds of communication in the organisation are crucial.

Limitations

According to the findings, the most significant obstacle to communication is language. In contrast, when all organisations were considered, psychological preconception was discovered to be the final and weakest obstacle. Other communication hurdles were erected between these two. In government sectors, the most and least communication barriers were found to be similar. In this area, though, intermediary barriers were a little different. Language was cited as the most significant barrier to communication by NGO personnel, whereas social power was considered as the least significant barrier. The most significant obstacle in this regard was counterparts in corporate chosen media, with psychological preconceived notions being the weakest barrier.

Suggestion towards better communication

In the current study, positive attitude emerged as the most essential tip for improving organisational communication, followed by effective team management, openness to adapt and share personal viewpoints, and employee support and cooperation. In the current study, equivalent suggestions from business employees were documented. The trend in mode of communication choice revealed that the working environment must have had a significant impact in determining preference for advocating organisational communication enhancement. Indirectly, the desired option could be interpreted as current organisational flaws. As a result, business sectors suffer from a lack of optimal positive attitude among employees, which could be linked to career competitiveness.

CONCLUSION

The tendency in medium of communication choice suggested that infrastructure must have had a significant impact in determining organisational communication preferences. The most

popular means of communication was determined to be e-mail, with fax being the least popular. The most essential recommendation for improving organisational communication was to have a positive mindset. Positive attitudes in the corporate sector, team management in non-government organisations, and employee support and cooperation in government institutions have all been identified as crucial and most critical intervention elements in strengthening relevant effective structure.

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